

THE ROLE OF EDUCATION IN SHAPING PERSONAL SPIRITUALITY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7509093>

Resume. The article mainly analyzes the specific features of national education in the formation of individual spirituality. In it, the views of the great thinkers of Karakalpak nation are mentioned about shaping personal spirituality.

Key words. Civilization, culture, values, person, society, education, life, system, classics, existence.

Our motherland, which was the cradle of great civilization and culture, has a great history since time immemorial, and raised man to the highest level of power. All the reforms implemented in our country today are for people. Every military action carried out in our country serves only the people and their needs. The new age, the new society demands from us a newly educated person who understands the truth of life.

A real person is a person who has great qualities, loves his country, strives for the future and understands the truth of life. Man has always sought to know his identity. All kinds of hypotheses and theories devoted to the problem of the individual have been created since ancient times and up to the present day. His life, freedom, rights, and value of a person made people think about all the historical eras. But with the passage of time, it seems that the human being has not been fully learned from me.

According to sages, what makes a person happy in life is not his money or physical strength, but his sincerity and wisdom. When a person understands the truth of life, he also achieves wisdom. Philosophy is considered the subject that leads to individual genius. If the most important problems of the "Person-world" system, the subject of philosophy, are listed, one aspect of this problem is what is a person and what is his place in the world? problems. The solution of this problem determines the importance of philosophy and the way of looking at the world.

Philosophy calls for understanding the natural and social content of a person, his place in the world, separate from other beings, self-understanding and the meaning of his life. In the 20th century philosophy, the greatest direction dealing with human nature is the direction of "existentialism" (esistenza - Latin "to exist"), which took shape in Europe during the first and second Soviet years. Major representatives are K. Jaspers M. Heidegger in Germany, J. P. Sartre and A. Camus in France.

This orientation, created during the war years, is aimed at understanding a person and his true nature, what is the purpose of creating a person, what is the real life of a person? He asks questions and searches. We will present the problem of the individual in the perspective of the problem of inhibition in the classical poems of Karakalpak Ajiniyaz and Berdak. Especially in Berdak's "Ómirim" and "Ayralıq" compositions, we find ideas about the true "exis" of a person. Ajiniyaz's poems "Ármanlı dúnya" and "Ótersen" depict ideas related to human nature.

Ajinyaz, who described man as the beauty of this world, shows that man has no place in this world. Human life, its beauty, understanding of one's own nature, understanding of life shows that it is the path leading to knowing one's own "existence". We can also see this in the example of existentialist philosophers, who proved that nothing can motivate a person to understand the truth of a beautiful life like art and literature. Most of them are written and counted. They knew that connection is a force that brings people closer to self-understanding. According to existentialists, a person can understand real life only when he is faced with "Life and Death". In order to understand the true existence of a person, one must face death. A person who is close to it cannot understand his true identity.

At the moment, the existence we have created, the actions we have, the world around us is fake, we cannot understand the real life because of our daily behavior. When a person feels that his life is wasted or sees the death of a close person, a person understands the real "exis". The orientation of existentialism divides human nature into two. True existence is what we strive to understand, and unreal existence is our daily way of life. Today, the civilizational development of humanity is very good, but it is very bad that people have lost their true identity. According to the German existentialist J.P. Sartre, "People understand themselves and what they are capable of in life by understanding the importance of their existence." True understanding of life saves him from special situations (accidents).

In particular, a person keeps his own identity from being spoiled. A person who dreams of his true identity does not know the value of anything, he also dreams that "Man and nature" are one and the same, using natural resources. He thinks that he is the most powerful person in the world. Ideas similar to these opinions can be found in the works of Karakalpak tar I. Yusupov. Every series of his essays "Bul dúnya" "Zaman ađımı" "Alasatlı dúnya bul" "Ómir aldanbaydı

adamnan biraq” and “Izleniw” are enriched with ideas about the life, death, and precious future of a person.

Today's nuclear wars, economic growth, anthropogenic impact on ecology will continue to such an extent that people will not be able to understand their true identity. One of the orientations of existentialism and one of the conceptual ideas is that man is considered to be the most important among the world's living creatures, that is, learning about man, who is the mainstay of the world, is considered the most important problem today. The philosophy of existentialism is a humanistic orientation that studies the individual uniqueness and uniqueness of a person, the meaningful content of a person's real life, his knowledge, his values, and the "World of Life" of a person. Existentialism philosophy studies - man, his fate in the modern world, faith, freedom, and the meaning of life are related to man. According to them, a person first exists, comes into the world, and only after that he is born. This means that a person does not have a pre-given nature. His existence in this world is defined by his existence. People strive to know themselves, wherever and whenever they do it. Existentialists of the 20th century raised this problem. We can see the relevance of this issue from the similarity of opinions of people with different worldviews and regions.

References:

1. Ш.М.Мирзиёев. «Янги Ўзбекистон стратегияси». – Тошкент: «O'zbekiston» нашриёти, 2021
2. Ясперс К. Смысл и назначение истории. М., 1991.
3. Biyimbetov J.K. Information Society Development Trends: Philosophical Analysis of Basic Concepts // Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies. – America: 2021. // ISSN 2770-0003. SJIF Impact Factor (2022): 5.909. –Б. 74-77.
4. Biyimbetov J.K. Political, economic, cultural and information development of the world in the process of globalization // Science and education in Karakalpakstan. Karakalpak State University name after Berdakh –Нукус: 2021. ISSN 2181-9203. –Р.91-92. (09.00.00; № 20).
5. Biyimbetov J.K. Philosophical analysis of the problem of information psychological security // Адам элэмі (Философский и общественно-гуманитарный журнал). –Kazakstan: 2021. ISSN №1999-5849. –Б. 3-9. (09.00.00; № 09).
6. Бийимбетов Ж.К. Қәуипсизликти тәмийнлеу мәселелериниң жәмийет турмысындағы әҳмийети // Бердақ номидаги Қорақалпоқ давлат университетининг Ахборотномаси. –Нукус: ҚДУ, 2020. ISSN 2010-9075. –Б. 174-175. (09.00.00; № 10).

7. Biyimbetov J.K. Problems of protection against threats affecting human consciousness in the processes of information civilization // 8th-International Conferenceon Research in Humanities, Applied Sciences and Education. Germany.: – Berlin: 2022. –P. 1-3.
8. Biyimbetov J.K. Philosophical characteristics of information security and analysis of human problems in the 21st century // International Conference on Developments in Education. Netherlands.: – Amsterdam: 2022. –P. 1-3.
9. Biyimbetov J.K. Socio-philosophical aspects of political culture formation in the process of globalization // Palarch’s journal of archaeology of egypt. – Egypt: 2020. ISSN: 1567-214X. –P. 100-109.
10. Мамбеткаримов Р.Р. Factors for Forming Critical Thinking in Students in the Educational Process // Research Journal of Humanities and Cultural Studies. 29-may 2022. Amerika. ISSN 2770-0003. SJIF Impact Factor (2022): 5.909. –Б. 1-4.
11. Мамбеткаримов Р.Р. Basic Principles and Methods of Using Media Education for forming Students’ Analytical Thinking // Zien Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities. 15-noyabr. 2021.Amerika. ISSN 2769-996X. SJIF Impact Factor (2021): 5.818. –Б. 63-68.
12. Mambetkarimov R.R. The problem of analytical thinking in the current modern education system // International Multidisciplinary Conference. England.: – Manchester: 2022. –P. 128-131.
13. Mambetkarimov R.R. The relationship between the development of analytical thinking and problem-based learning in quality education // 8th-International Conferenceon Research in Humanities, Applied Sciences and Education., Germany.: – Berlin: 2022. –P. 77-81.
14. Tlepbergenova Perizat. Ecology of the Bukhara Deer in Our Country (Distribution and Origin). Research Journal of Applied Medical Sciences. 25.04.2022. 16-бет.
15. Tlepbergenova Perizat. Prospects For the Development of Ecological Tourism in Uzbekistan. Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies. 2021-йил 15-ноябрь. 144-бет.
16. Tlepbergenova Perizat. Global ecological problems: Essence and possible solutions. International Journal of Academic Multidisciplinary Research (IJAMR). 2021-йил 5-май. 108-бет.
17. Usmonov M. T. Means of Information Protection. International Journal of Academic and Applied Research (IJAAR) ISSN: 2643-9603 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 27-30.

18. Usmonov M. T. Organization of E-Mail Protection. International Journal of Academic Engineering Research (IJAER) ISSN: 2643-9085 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 36-40.
19. Usmonov M. T. Organizing Internet Protection. International Journal of Academic Engineering Research (IJAER) ISSN: 2643-9085 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 24-28.
20. Usmonov M. T. Origin and Equal Strength Relationships between Sentences. Necessary and Sufficient Conditions. Structure of Theorem and Their Types. International Journal of Engineering and Information Systems (IJEAIS) ISSN: 2643-640X Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 45-47.
21. Usmonov M. T. Physical Security. International Journal of Academic and Applied Research (IJAAR) ISSN: 2643-9603 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 58-61.
22. Usmonov M. T. Practical Security Management. International Journal of Academic Engineering Research (IJAER) ISSN: 2643-9085 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 71-74.
23. Usmonov M. T. Problem Solving In Primary Schools. International Journal of Academic Information Systems Research (IJAISR) ISSN: 2643-9026 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 72-83.
24. Usmonov M. T. Reproduction. The Laws of Reproduction. International Journal of Engineering and Information Systems (IJEAIS) ISSN: 2643-640X Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 36-40.
25. Usmonov M. T. Security Models. International Journal of Academic Pedagogical Research (IJAPR) ISSN: 2643-9123 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 18-23.
26. Usmonov M. T. Solving Problems In Arithmetic Methods. International Journal of Academic Information Systems Research (IJAISR) ISSN: 2643-9026 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 58-61.

